

SUFIS AND SUFISM IN THE TERRITORY OF KALPI—15TH AND 16TH CENTURIES

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The fifteenth century in the history of north India is a period of great cultural significance, but little work has been done on it. Many aspects of the Indo-Muslim Culture during the subsequent centuries, particularly the background of the rise of religious trends, both revivalist and syncretic, would remain obscure unless a detailed and indepth study is made of life and culture in the fifteenth century. No doubt, the Delhi Sultanate disintegrated towards the close of the 14th century, giving rise to centrifugal tendencies, the legacy of its cultural and political system, however, remained. Soon certain *Muqtas* and *zamindārs* managed to seize neighbouring territories, established peace and order there and thus carved out independent kingdoms and principalities for themselves. The hagiological literature as well as chronicles, produced in these kingdoms provide interesting information not only about the proliferation of the Muslim culture developed in Delhi but also shed considerable light on the activities of the *Ṣūfī* saints who had migrated from Delhi to different cities on the eve of Timūr's invasion in 1398 A.D. Many of these *Ṣūfīs*, known for spiritual qualities and excellence settled in Kalpi, the capital of a newly-founded principality, and considerably contributed to the process of urbanization in the region.

The contemporary historian of Kalpi would have us believe that owing to the coming of the *Ṣūfīs* and *ʿulama* (religious scholars) from Delhi, the village of Kalpi where the influence of Islamic faith and culture had not permeated so far was soon transformed into an Islamic Centre.¹ Besides their services and devotion to religion and its cause, many *Ṣūfīs* seem to have also played an important role in disseminating knowledge of Islamic sciences and making Kalpi a seat of Muslim learning and culture. The aim of this paper is to present a brief account of the emergence of Kalpi as an important urban centre and analyse the relevant evidence with regard to the cultural role played by the *Ṣūfīs* in the region. Attempt has also been

made to study the influence of the Hindu *Yogis* on the *Şufis* and vice versa during the 15th and 16th centuries.

The small village of Kalpi,² surrounded by forests began to grow into a city when Malikzāda Maḥmūd Turk, having been driven away by Rai Sabir and Rai Adhran, the chauhan *zamindars* of Etawah and Bhogam respectively, from the *shiqq* (province) of Firozpur, made it his headquarter in 1390 A.D.³ Shortly afterwards the Malikzāda was joined by many other nobles who also had to vacate their forts and *iqtas*, such as Tughluqpūr, (former Akhal), Phapond, Chandwar, Shamsābād, Patiali etc. under the threat posed by the rebel chiefs of the region.⁴ All of them came to Kalpi with their dependants and followers with the result that it rapidly developed into a city of great importance. Being resourceful, they built houses for their residence with mosques and *madrasas* adjacent to them. Malikzāda Maḥmūd seems to have taken pains to develop Kalpi as a Centre of culture. He demarcated fairly large area, encircled it with strong and lofty walls and then diverted much of his resources towards the building of massive palace fortress.⁵ A number of mosques and other buildings of public utility were also erected. On the completion of the Hişar (fortification) the ruler named his city as Muḥammadābād after the Prophet of Islam.⁶

On the sack of Delhi by Timūr, Malikzāda Maḥmūd Turk assumed independence with the title of Sulṭān Maḥmūd Shāh. He extended generous help to all those scholars, *Şufis*, sayyids and artisans who fled from Delhi and other disturbed areas and sought asylum in Muḥammadābād alias Kalpi. As a result of the influx of people, Kalpi became '*Shahri Mu'azzam* (great city) and became famous as Muḥammadābād alias Kalpi.⁷

The early *Şufis* of Kalpi chiefly belonged to the Chishti and Suhrawardi *silsilahs* (orders). Afterwards, the Zāhidi,⁸ Shaṭṭari⁹ and Madāria *Şufis* were also attracted by Kalpi's fame. Every one of them tried to turn Kalpi into a centre of his *silsilah*. No doubt, genuine spirituality was the concern of few in medieval times, as it is today, many *Şufis* sincerely endeavoured to wean away people from the lures of the worldly life and also provided them with solace in distress. The fact that most of these saints are mentioned by Shaikh 'Abdul Ḥaque Muḥaddith of Delhi in his *Akḥbar-u'l-Akḥiyar* (a biographical work) indicates that they were eminent *Şufis* and had left their mark in their field of endeavour. We may now analyse their activities

in Kalpi and the area around on the basis of genuine evidence available in the standard and pristine *Şufi* sources.

Most prominent of the *Şufis* who took abode in Kalpi on a permanent basis was Shaikh Aḥmad Thanesari, son of Maulana Muḥammad⁹ Thanesari.¹⁰ His learning and association with Shaikh Naşir al-Din Chirāgh of Delhi as a *murid* (disciple) and *khalifa* (spiritual successor) made him a popular saint in Delhi during the later half of the 14th century. It is said that he was arrested by the soldiers of Timūr along with a large number of his disciples in Delhi in 1398 but his profound knowledge of religious sciences helped him in securing his own release and of his disciples as well. Timur is reported to have been deeply impressed by his mastery over Hanafite *fiqh* (jurisprudence).¹¹ On his release, he left for Kalpi where he was received by the Sulṭān. In Kalpi, people belonging to different strata of the society became his *murid*. Being an orthodox *Şufi*, he imparted instructions in Islamic jurisprudence, emphasising the importance of complete adherence to *shari'a* (religious law). In fact, the Chishti *silsilah* gained popularity in Kalpi because of his presence there. On his death, Aḥmad Kḥān, the younger brother of Sulṭān Maḥmūd Turk and one of the Shaikh's faithful *murids* had a beautiful dome constructed over his grave inside the fortification.¹²

Some of the distinguished disciples and *khalifas* of Sayyid Muḥammad Gısdarāz (the *khalifa* of Shaikh Naşir al-Din Chirāgh of Delhi) also settled in Kalpi. For example Shaikh Alā al-Din Qureshī and Shaikh Abul Faṭḥ 'Ala'i were also the leading Chishti saints, who had settled in Kalpi, sometime after the invasion of Timur. The former hailed from Gwalior. He generally lived in seclusion, spending his time in prayer to God.¹³ The latter lived in the midst of people, wrote a number of treatises on *Şufism* and taught his disciples esoteric as well as exoteric sciences.¹⁴ After his death, his rich disciples built a grand tomb over his grave in 1450. This is built of stone and brick in lime and is covered with lime plaster. Its lofty dome carved on an octagonal drum is bulbous. The inscription fixed on the southern doorway calls him Zāir-ul Ḥaramain (one who paid visit to the *ḥarams* in Mecca and Madina).¹⁵

The important Suhrawardi saint who won followers among various sections of people in Kalpi was Shaikh Sirāj Sokhta. He was also a profound scholar. First, he committed the Qur'an to memory and then studied other popular sciences of his time. For his deep learning, he was included among the distinguished pupils of Maulāna

Naḥvī like Qādi Shihāb al-Din Daulatābādī. It was due to his learning that Shaiḥ Jalāl al-Din Bukhārī, popularly known as Makhdūm-i Jahāniān-i Jahāngasht selected him as one of his *khalifas*. In Kalpi, he did not find it difficult to attract people in a large number. His *murids* included several important nobles of Kalpi. Even Shah Qādir Shah, son and successor of Sulṭān Maḥmūd Turk (1411-1432 A.D.) is reported to have held him in high esteem for his learning and spiritual eminence.¹⁶

Mention should also be made of Shaiḥ Yūsuf Buda Erachi who also happened to be one of the prominent disciples of Makhdūm-i Jahāniān-i Jahāngasht. Being a distinguished scholar of Arabic, known for his mastery over Islamic doctrinal and Shūfi texts, abundance of literary compositions and a refined sensibility to poetry, he had become one of the most popular and respectable Shūfis of north India. He is also credited with having written a number of books. His translation of Imām Ghazālī's *Minhāj-ul 'Abidīn* in *Mathnavi* form, consisting two thousand five hundred and twenty verses and named as *Fatūhāt-i Ahmad* was very popular like his *diwan* (the collection of poems). Like the Chishtī Shūfis, he was also fond of *sama* (listening to devotional songs) and considered it as a means to spiritual development. In 1430 he attended a *sama* party in which he passed into an ecstatic state. He is reported to have remained in this state of mystic intoxication for several days and then passed away in Erach. It may, however, be pointed out that the biographical notices contained in the *Tariḥ-i Muḥammadi* tend to show that the Shaiḥ was never negligent of social obligations incumbent upon a Shūfi of his eminence. He took his duty of instructing his *murids* seriously and maintained the traditions of his *silsilah*.¹⁷ Maḥmūd Khān (son of Mughīth Khān), later Sulṭān 'Alā al-Din Maḥmūd Shah Khilji of Malwa had a mausoleum constructed over his grave. Its dome was known for its loftiness.¹⁸

Another Suhrawardi Shūfi of distinction was Shaiḥ 'Abdul Ḥakīm, popularly known as *Goshanashīn*. He was the *khalifa* of al-Ḥāj Shaiḥ 'Abdul Wahhāb Bukhārī (died in 1525 A.D.). His qualities, such as austerity of an orthodox character and resignation to the will of Allah greatly contributed to his prestige and popularity. He is also said to have lived most of the time in a state of ecstasy. He passed away in Kalpi in 1574.¹⁹

As regards the *zāhidi silsilah*, Shaiḥ Bahā al-Din Ganj-i Ravān introduced it in Kalpi during the reign of Sulṭān Qādir Shāh. Both the members of ruling elite and commoners had faith in him. Ghauthī Shattārī informs us that the Sulṭān and his officers offered him cash, villages and gardens but he never accepted any gift from them. Nevertheless, he fed a large number of people daily and for this reason was called by people as *Ganj-i-Ravān* (never ending treasure). Towards the end of his life he occupied an unclaimed tract of land on the bank of Jamuna and carried on cultivation there. He built a house also and planted a garden. The spiritual qualities, possessed by him to an impressive degree, helped his successors to keep their *silsilah* alive after him.²⁰

Similarly, the founder of the *Madāriya silsilah* in India, Shaiḥ Badi' al-Din, popularly known as Shāh Madār came to Kalpi during the reign of Qādir Shāh. He was a Syrian Shūfi of Jewish origin. On his conversion to Islam, he got himself enrolled among the disciples of Shaiḥ Ṭaifūr Shāmī. He acquired mastery over Ibn-i 'Arabi's metaphysical philosophy known as *Wahdat-u'l-Wujūd*, in addition to his knowledge of Jewish and Christian practices of mysticism. However, the paucity of authentic information about him makes it somewhat difficult to attempt a detailed mention of his life and teachings. The seventeenth century writers (such as 'Abd al-Raḥman Chishtī, the author of *Mirat-i-Madāriya*) have horribly confused facts with fiction and have incorporated in their works all that they found floating down the stream of time. In fact, they wrote when the followers of the *Madāriya silsilah* had begun to indulge in all sorts of vices in complete disregard of the teachings of their great Shaiḥ. The odd bits pieced from different standard works reveal that he was respected and held by the leading Shūfis to be in the first rank of the Indian Muslim Shūfis. He commanded great respect among others as well for his religiosity and piety. He was not opposed to the observance of Muslim rituals also. For instance, a contemporary inscription found in a step-well in Chanderi, dated 1436, mentions the builder of the well Taghī, the learned Wazir at the court of Malwa along with his *pīr*, Shāh Madār. The latter has been mentioned as the great, pious and religious-minded saint.²¹ Likewise the anecdote about the saint, contained in the *Mulfuẓāt* of Shāh Minā sheds interesting light on his popularity during his lifetime. Shāh Minā calls him the King of saintly people and pays reverential homage to him as a pious Shūfi.²²

In Kalpi Shāh Madār got in close touch with the Hindu *Jogis* and seems to have acquired knowledge of Nāthapanthi Yogis' physiological concepts and accepted some of their practices. The testimony of Shaikh 'Abdul Ḥaque Muḥaddith Dehlavi is of immense significance in this regard. According to it, Shāh Madār was very fond of the company of the *Jogis* and discussed with them problems relating to Hindu mysticism.²³ The association of the Ṣūfīs with the *Jogis* was not at all objectionable during the 15th century. Some of the leading Chiṣṭī saints also adopted certain yogic traditions. For instance, Shaikh 'Abdul Ḥaque Radaulvi and 'Abdul Quddūs Gangohī regularly did the exercises of controlling breath, burying themselves alive for some time or the practise of devotion performed upside down while hanging suspended by a rope tied to the heels.²⁴

A few words may be added about his departure from Kalpi to the Sharqī Kingdom of Jaunpur. It is said that he refused to receive Qādir Shāh of Kalpi who was desirous of calling on him. Feeling insulted, the Sultān asked Shāh Madār to leave his territory. Thereupon Shāh Madār went to Jaunpur and finally settled down in Mākanpūr, a small town now included in the district of Kanpur.²⁵ One of his disciples and successors, Qaḍī Maḥzar, however, stayed in Kalpi. Ghauthī Shaṭṭārī states that he was an 'Alim, a deep Ṣūfī and sincerely devoted to the cause of religion.²⁶

In the end we may devote same space to Shaikh Burhān Anṣārī, another prominent Ṣūfī saint of Kalpi. Devoted to religion and piety, he always preferred a life of abject poverty to that of comfort. He spent his time either in offering prayers in his cell or imparting knowledge of religious sciences. In public lectures that he delivered daily, he explained the significance of the Qurānic verses. Mulla 'Abdul Qādir Badaoni when paid a visit to him in Kalpi found him more than hundred years old.²⁷ People considered him a Mehdavi but Ghauthī Shaṭṭārī states that this charge was not borne out by facts. Shaikh Burhān Anṣārī composed verses in Hindvi as well as in Persian. His *diwan*, entitled *Firaqnāma* was available in the 17th century. Praising it, Ghauthī Shaṭṭārī says that every line of the *diwan* is full of pathos and effect.²⁸

NOTES

¹ Muḥammad Bihāmad khāni, *Tārīkh-i Muḥammadi*, Ms. British Museum, Or. 137, ff. 441b, 451 ab.

² Kalpi is the headquarters of a tehsil of the same name in the district of Jalaun, Uttar Pradesh, site 26° 81N. 79° 45'E on the Jamuna river, 22 miles away from the district headquarters.

³ *Tārīkh-i Muḥammadi*, f. 418b.

⁴ *Tārīkh-i Muḥammadi*, f.

⁵ *Ibid.*, ff. 419b, 450a-51a.

⁶ *Ibid.*, f. 443a.

⁷ Zāhidi *silsilah* was founded in India by Shaikh al Fakhr al-Dīn Zāhidi, a contemporary of Shaikh Quṭb al-Dīn Bakhtiyār Kākī. He lies buried in Meerut (U.P.). Cf. Ghauthī Shaṭṭārī *Gulzār-i-Abrār*, Urdu tr. *Azkar-i Abrar*, Muhammad Qadir Ṣūfī, pp. 45-46, hereafter cited as *Gulzār-i-Abrār*, Urdu. tr.

⁸ Cf. Prof. K.A. Nizāmī, 'Shaṭṭārī Saints And Their Attitude towards the State', *Medieval India*, Quarterly, Aligarh, vol. I, No. 2, October 1950, pp. 56-70.

⁹ *Tārīkh-i Muḥammadi*, f. 443a.

¹⁰ Shaikh 'Abdul Haque Muḥaddith Dehlavi, *Akhbar-ul-Akhiyar*, ed. Shaikh Zafar 'Ali, Aḥmadi Press, Delhi, undated, p. 166.

¹¹ *Tārīkh-i Muḥammadi*, f. 443a.

¹² *Akhbar-ul Akhiyar*, p. 185.

¹³ *Ibid.*, p. 188.

¹⁴ The inscription runs:

گنبد شیخ زائیر الحر مین شیخ ابوالفتح قطب اهل زمان
در بلندی شدت رشک فلک در لطافت شدت رشک جنان
بود بنیاد وے به هشت صدوسه بعد پنجاه در مہه شعبان
شد ازان پس به هفت ماه تمام ذر صفر از عنایت یزدان

(The tomb of the Shaikh, the visitor of the two herams; Shaikh Abu'l Fath, the Pole Star of the world. It is an object of envy for the skies on account of its loftiness; and envied by paradise for its elegance. Its foundation was laid in the month of Sha'bān in the year 803 plus 50 (853 A.H.—Sep. 1449 A.D.). It was completed seven months later; in the month of Ṣafar by the grace of God.) (*Epigraphia Indica*, A.P.S., *op. cit.*, 1953-54, pp. 35-36).

¹⁵ *Akhbar-ul-Akhiyar*, p. 188.

¹⁶ *Tārīkh-i Muḥammadi*, ff. 169b-173b.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*, ff. 174, 174a. *Akhbar-ul-Akhiyar*, p. 178. Erach is included in the district of Jhansi in Uttar Pradesh.

¹⁸ *Gulzār-i Abrār*, Urdu tr. p. 318.

¹⁹ *Gulzār-i Abrār*, Urdu tr. pp. 192-99.

²⁰ Cf. *Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic and Persian Supplement, ed. Z.A. Desai, 1964.

²¹ *Malḥūzāt-i Haḍrat Shaikh Muḥammad, al-Ma'rūf-ba-Shaikh Mina*, Muḥi al-Dīn bin Ḥusain Rizvi al-Ḥusaini, Ms. Hābib Ganj Collection, Aligarh, no. 21/244 Farsi, ff. 77b-78a.

²² *Akhbar-ul-Akhiyar*, p. 188.

²³ Cf. Simon Degby, 'Abdul Quddūs Gangohī: The Personality and Attitudes of a Medieval Indian Sufi', *Medieval India. A Miscellany*, Vol. 3, Aligarh, 1975, pp. 36-39.

²⁴ *Akḥbar-ul-Akḥiyar*, p. 188.

²⁵ *Gulzār-i Abrār*, Urdu tr. p. 77.

²⁶ *Muntakḥab-u't-Tawarīkh*, iii/6-7.

²⁷ *Gulzār-i Abrār*, Urdu tr. p. 305.

BHAKTI AND ISHQ-E-ILAHİ

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Among Indian religions *Bhakti* is that trend of religiosity which is characterised by a loving devotion to one Supreme Object of worship. The devotional attitude towards the Deity and a monotheistic concept of the Object of worship being two basic elements of *Bhakti-marga*, it can be said to be basically distinct from the Brahmanical or Vedic religious tradition which was polytheistic and sacrificial in character. Hence the contention of writers like P. Banarjee and Dines Chander Sarkar that *Bhakti* is essentially a non-Brahmanical and non-Aryan religious tradition.¹ Narda in his famous *Bhakti Sutras* has described *Bhakti* thus:

It is of the form of supreme love of this (i.e., God).
And its proper nature (is) immortal;
obtaining which man becomes perfect,
becomes immortal, becomes satisfied.
Attaining which (he) does not desire anything, does not
sorrow, does not hate, does not enjoy and does not become
excitedly active (for anything else). It (Divine love is)
not lust, because its form is control. But control (is) the
consecration (or renunciation) of profane and vedic acti-
vities, exclusiveness (of devotion) in Him and indifference
for what is contrary to Him.²

The earliest reference to a religion based on an attitude described above and directed towards One Supreme Lord, called Vasudeva, is found in *Panini* (500 B.C. *Sutra* iv, iii, 98) where Vasudeva is referred to as god of gods.³ A Krishna-Vasudeva son of Devaki is also referred to in *Chandogya Upanishad* (700 B.C.) where some religious instruction is imparted to him. If the essence of this religious instruction is established to correspond to the teachings of Bhagvata religion, as seems quite probable, then the date of the earliest reference to *Bhakti* may be pushed back to 700 B.C. On the authority of *Chadogya Upanishad*, the *Mahabharata* and some inscriptions such